

Pattern determination of the territory local factors influence on the land plots' cadastral value of gardening and horticultural non-profit partnerships

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Received 6 November 2023 ♦ **Accepted** 16 January 2024 ♦ **Published** 22 October 2024

Citation: Banikevich TD, Bykova EN, Zalivatskaya NV, Pirogova OE (2024) Pattern determination of the territory local factors influence on the land plots' cadastral value of gardening and horticultural non-profit partnerships. *Population and Economics* 8(3):86-107. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.8.e115183>

Abstract

In recent decades, the state has been tasked with the effective management of natural resources, among which land resources hold particular importance due to the necessity of their rational use and sustainable development. The value of land resources and their indispensable role in ensuring the socio-economic development of the country is most clearly reflected in the state's tax policy, specifically in land taxation. The amount of land tax depends on the cadastral value, which is often subject to methodological shortcomings and challenges. This study, using the Belgorod Region as a case study, proposes an algorithm for determining the cadastral value of land plots within gardening and horticultural non-profit partnerships, taking local factors into account. To determine the specific indicator of cadastral value (SICV) of land plots, a linear regression model was developed. The results, tested for homoscedasticity, confirmed the model's adequacy and reliability. The findings showed that the cadastral value decreased by an average of 12.2% compared to the current results of the state cadastral assessment in the Belgorod Region, highlighting the influence of local factors and the importance of considering them in the cadastral evaluation of the land plots in question.

Keywords

cadastral valuation, land tax, modeling, soil quality, relief, moisture supply, well, remoteness

JEL codes: H2, R30

Introduction

Within the concept of sustainable territorial development, which is a key paradigm of modern global development, land resources – like other components of the natural environment such as water, forests, and minerals – play a critical role (Golovina & Grebneva 2022; Marinina et al. 2022; Vasilev et al. 2020). However, assessing progress towards sustainable development goals remains challenging, largely due to the ongoing development of science, technology, and – most importantly – the valuation of natural resources like land (Yurak et al. 2020).

In land assessments, determining cadastral value is especially pertinent, as it directly affects land tax calculations (Wang & Li 2019). Particular attention should be given to land intended for gardening and vegetable cultivation. Such lands, along with agricultural land, contribute to the country's food security. Moreover, the owners of these lands often belong to vulnerable segments of society, for whom fair land taxation is crucial.

Notably, over the past three years, the number of registered garden plots in the Russian Federation has increased by 30%. The Union of Gardeners of Russia estimates that approximately 60 million citizens belong to this category (Government of Russia 2023). However, according to the 2006 and 2016 agricultural censuses (All-Russian Agricultural... 2006, 2016), the area of agricultural land plots in horticultural non-profit partnerships (GNPPs) and agricultural non-profit partnerships (ANPPs) across Russia has been decreasing.

Yet, in regions such as the Belgorod Region – one of the country's leading agricultural areas – high agricultural productivity, along with the use of GNPP and ANPP land, helps ensure regional food security. In many countries, the gardening sector is a vital source of employment and income for low-income populations (Azadi & Vanhoute 2019). This trend may point to the active development of GNPPs as an expanding sector within the land market.

It is worth paying attention to the growing interest of the scientific community, which deals with issues of cadastral valuation of land resources, and, to one degree or another, tries to solve emerging problems in this area. Russian scientist S.V. Gribovsky in his works pays sufficient attention to the issues of assessing the quality and improving the methodological apparatus of cadastral valuation of real estate (Gribovsky 2019). A significant part of the scientific works of A.V. Sevostyanov is devoted to the assessment of land in populated areas (Sevostyanov 2006). P.M. Sapozhnikov deals with issues of assessing agricultural land to a greater extent (Sapozhnikov & Granina 2021). The team of authors represented by S.A. Galchenko, R.V. Zhdanova, S.I. Komarov and A.A. Rasskazova try to resolve existing problems in the field of cadastral valuation of agricultural lands, offering alternative methods and solutions (Galchenko et al. 2020). Researchers such as T.I. Baltyzhakova, O.Yu. Lepikhina and I.G. Raguzin pay attention to improving the procedure for conducting cadastral valuation of real estate (Baltyzhakova & Raguzin 2020; Lepikhina et al. 2020).

Currently, many Russian and foreign authors are addressing the issue of accounting for various factors that influence changes in the cadastral value of land. O.Yu. Lepikhina and E.A. Pravdina, for instance, propose considering a variable accounting of social infrastructure factors. They suggest three approaches to accounting for such factors: the remoteness from the assessed object to the infrastructure; the area of the assessed object within the infrastructure's accessibility zone; and the number of infrastructure objects within the accessibility radius. These factors have all been shown to influence cadastral value (Lepikhina & Pravdina 2019).

Similarly, N.A. Alekseeva identifies the socio-economic development of a region as a key factor (Alekseeva 2018). A. Bangayan-Manera also advocates for considering economic and social factors, including urban planning, environmental considerations, and factors related to the intended use of the land, during cadastral valuations of land within settlements (Bangayan-Manera et al. 2021). A. Agosto, focusing on land plots intended for residential construction, identified 11 factors that influence the cost of such plots. These factors are categorized into economic, legal, and quality-of-life factors (such as the availability of open spaces, parks, recreation areas, plot size, and environmental quality) (Agosto 2020).

In relation to forest lands, V.F. Kovyazin, A.A. Kitsenko, and Seyed Omid Reza Shobayri proposed considering the degree of infrastructure development as a cost factor (Kovyazin et al. 2021). A.L. Zhelyaskov and D.E. Seturidze extended this idea to agricultural land, emphasizing the importance of infrastructure development, social, and demographic indicators (Zhelyaskov & Seturidze 2020). Zhuravlev E.G. and Konovalov E.V. highlighted the presence of a water body as a significant factor influencing cadastral value (Zhuravlev & Konovalova 2014).

I.S. Dyachkova proposed the inclusion of historical and cultural factors in the assessment of land within settlements (Kovyazin et al. 2020). Lastly, a team of authors, including V.N. Berdnikova, A.V. Osennyaya, and B.A. Khahuk, considered socio-economic factors such as the development of small and medium-sized businesses and the size of the permanent resident population as important influences on cadastral value (Berdnikova et al. 2021).

In addition, some researchers consider factors that can reduce cadastral value. For example, V.S. Gorbunov, S.I. Shorokhov, and P.S. Bragina identified air pollution, noise, and vibration pollution of adjacent territories as contributing to a reduction in cadastral value (Gorbunov et al. 2013). E.L. Kuleshova also studied the impact of soil pollution (Kuleshova 2003). However, it is worth noting that the development of methods to account for value-reducing factors is currently quite limited. The impact of these factors on the market value of land can be difficult to assess, as they are often external and hard to quantify.

When discussing the comprehensive consideration of factors influencing cadastral value, it is important to highlight the role of encumbrances (restrictions) on land, such as zones with special conditions of territorial use (ZSCUT). Several Russian authors, including A.A. Varlamov (Varlamov & Kirillov 2017), E.N. Bykova (Bykova 2021), V.Yu. Sutyagin (Sutyagin 2017), K.E. Senkovskaya (Senkovskaya 2014), and Yu.V. Chernetskaya (Chernetskaya & Kiselev 2014), have developed methods that account for such encumbrances by introducing correction factors. These methods have proven effective in achieving more accurate results in determining cadastral land values.

In relation to agricultural lands, including garden and vegetable plots, researchers have pointed out methodological and practical challenges in assessing value. S.E. Badmaeva and I.S. Andryushchenko, for example, used factor analysis to identify hidden price factors such as transport infrastructure accessibility, the prestige of the area, and the distance to public transport stops (Badmaeva & Andryushchenko 2020). L. Meissner and O. Musshoff demonstrated the influence of soil quality on agricultural land value (Meissner & Musshoff 2022), a finding echoed by J. Choumert in studies of land in Argentina (Choumert & Phélinas 2015). Additionally, E. Lote and F.O. Tavares highlighted how factors such as location, market dynamics, water availability, proximity to tourist destinations, and the physical condition of agricultural fields can either positively or negatively impact land value in Huambo Province, Angola (Lote & Tavares 2023).

At the same time, when analyzing the existing challenges in assessing agricultural land, A.E. Sagaidak and A.A. Sagaidak propose conducting auctions for such lands. This approach

would allow the formation of an equilibrium market price by balancing supply and demand. The starting auction price of the land itself, for instance, could serve as the basis for calculating land tax rates and other land-related transactions (Sagaidak & Sagaidak 2020). S.A. Mamantova and O.P. Kolpakova, on the other hand, emphasize the importance of considering the individual characteristics of land plots. In their research on cost factor differentiation in the municipalities of the Krasnoyarsk Territory, they highlight the need to account for the qualitative state of soils. They suggest replacing the generalized factor “Landscape and environmental attractiveness” with several more specific factors, such as distance to the nearest body of water, distance to pollution sources, and proximity to unique landmarks. Additionally, they proposed a procedure for coordinating the final list of cost factors for the lands of horticultural and vegetable gardening associations with local authorities (Mamantova & Kolpakova 2018).

An analysis of scientific research on the cadastral valuation of land resources shows increasing interest in addressing the issues related to determining the cadastral value of agricultural land and gardening associations’ lands. This includes exploring various combinations of cost factors that influence land value, as well as developing methodologies to improve the current systems for determining cadastral value. However, unresolved issues remain in both science and practice, particularly concerning the incorporation of local factors into the cadastral valuation of gardening lands. These local factors include proximity to railway stations, municipal solid waste (MSW) storage sites, soil quality, topography, and more, all of which affect the variation in cadastral value.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The primary objective of this study is to enhance the objectivity of cadastral valuation results for garden and vegetable garden lands by developing proposals that incorporate local cost factors. Achieving this goal involves addressing the following tasks: justifying the composition of local factors that influence the cadastral value of land plots within the segment of “Gardening and Horticulture, Low-Rise Residential Development”; developing proposals for modifying the cadastral valuation procedure to account for these local cost factors; calculating the cadastral value of garden and vegetable garden lands in the Belgorod region; conducting a comparative analysis of the calculated cadastral values against the current results of the state cadastral valuation of land plots in the Belgorod region to validate the effectiveness of the proposed modifications to the methodology.

The object of this study is the cadastral value of land plots within the specified segment in the Belgorod district of the Belgorod region. The scientific novelty of this research lies in determining the influence of local factors on the cadastral value and in modifying the methodology for cadastral valuation of lands in the segment of “Gardening and Horticulture, Low-Rise Residential Development.”

Research methodology

The scientific research was carried out using a comprehensive and systemic approach, which is due to the specifics of the methodological apparatus of cadastral valuation of land plots. For the scientific review of studies by Russian and foreign authors, methods of synthesis,

analysis, comparison, analogy, and generalization were employed. Methods at the empirical and theoretical levels, including observation, experimentation, and description, were utilized in collecting initial market data. The creation of a GIS project for the visualization and processing of initial market data was based on the functionality of the MapInfo software product. When performing calculations, MS Excel add-ins, correlation and regression analysis, statistical data processing methods, and mathematical modeling were applied.

The object of implementation of the proposals considered in this work was the Belgorod region of the Russian Federation, where the state cadastral valuation (GKO) of land plots, including the segment “Gardening and Horticulture, Low-Rise Residential Development,” was last carried out in 2022. Among the cost factors affecting the cadastral value of the lands in the segment under consideration, those presented in Figure 1 were taken into account [Center for State Cadastral Valuation of the Belgorod Region].

	Distance to the administrative center of the settlement
	Distance to the nearest public transport stop
	Remoteness from the settlement to Belgorod
	Remoteness from the settlement to the center of the municipal area
	Availability of central sewerage in the locality
	Availability of central water supply in the locality
	Population in a municipal area, urban district
	Average monthly salary by municipalities, urban districts
	Urban/rural settlement center

Figure 1. List of cost factors. *Source:* (Center for State Cadastral... 2023)

As practice shows, the methodology for determining cadastral value, which is used by appraisers, does not always reflect the real value of a land plot, as it does not take into account a significant number of market pricing factors and tends to be of a generalized nature (Ciuna et al. 2017). The consequence of an incorrect composition of cadastral value factors is an inflated land tax. Therefore, within the framework of this work, it is proposed to study the influence of local cost factors on the cadastral value of the lands in question. Such factors, in the context of this work, are those that can be identified directly on the territory of the assessed gardening non-profit partnership (GNPP), horticultural non-profit partnership (ANPP), as well as on the territory of individual housing construction (IHC), hypothetically influencing the value of a specific land plot.

The market value of land plots in these entities is associated with the loss of their property during the implementation of economic, managerial, and business activities, taking into account the totality of cost factors affecting the value. The cancellation of the Technical Instructions on the state cadastral value of lands of horticultural, gardening, and dacha

associations, approved by the Order of Roszemkadastr dated 06/05/2002, which presented an approximate list of factors, has made it possible for appraisers to determine their composition. However, the choice and composition of factors constraining the value of land have become subjective in nature and do not always lead, for example, to obtaining an objective measure of cadastral value. This context serves as a basis for the definition of the list of local cost factors presented in Table 1.

Table 1. List of studied local factors for cadastral valuation of land plots of GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction

№	Name of local factor	Units
1	2	3
1	Distance to railway station	km
2	Soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction	B
3	Relief inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction, slope	%
4	Availability of a capital construction project on the land plot	Yes/no
5	Availability of a well	Yes/no
6	Remoteness from solid waste storage areas.	m

Source: (Center for State Cadastral... 2023)

The choice of local factors presented in Table 1 is based on the following circumstances:

1. Factor: Distance to the Railway Station.

The transport accessibility of associations located outside populated areas directly depends on railway connections, as individuals who do not have the opportunity to travel by car will prefer railway transport. Statistically, this factor plays a decisive role in the market pricing of a land plot, as potential buyers are more likely to prefer purchasing land plots that are closer to transport links.

2. Factor: Soil Quality Inside GNPP, ANPP, and Individual Housing Construction.

Since 1949, free lands in cities, towns, enterprises, and institutions, as well as plots in the right-of-way of railway lines and highways, have been transferred for vegetable gardens. Later, dachas were established on agricultural lands with a high level of soil fertility and on forest lands through uprooting and partial destruction of forest vegetation. Consequently, the associations under consideration may now be located on lands with varying levels of soil fertility, and one partnership may contain land plots situated within the boundaries of different soil varieties. For example, Fig. 2 presents the GNPP “Severyane” in the Belgorod region, which features three types of soils.

In accordance with Federal Law No. 217-FZ dated July 29, 2017, one of the main types of use for such plots is the cultivation of agricultural crops, making soil quality an important criterion for purchasing a land plot (Federal Law, 2017). Land plots of GNPP and ANPP located on forest lands are more often subject to water erosion and excessive flooding, which leads to a decrease in fertility and, as a rule, can affect the market pricing of these land plots.

3. Factor: Relief Inside GNPP, ANPP, and Individual Housing Construction, Slope.

When discussing the significance of this factor, it is important to note that, firstly, the relief of the Russian Federation is quite diverse and characterized by variations in elevation. The lack of consideration for its influence on the value of land plots can create discrepancies between the cadastral data and the actual area of the land. Secondly, the topography of the

territory affects moisture supply for vegetation, the choice of crops grown, and the organization of anti-erosion measures. Consequently, land plots located in flooded low-lying areas are generally less in demand among buyers compared to those situated in dry, elevated areas. Figure 3 illustrates the relief within the boundaries of the GNPP “Severyane” (Unified State Register of Soil Resources of Russia).

Figure 2. Soil types within the boundaries of GNPP “Severyane”, Belgorod region. *Source:* (Information system... 2023)

Figure 3. Relief within the boundaries of GNPP “Severyane”, Belgorod region. *Source:* (Unified State Register...)

4. Factor: Availability of a Capital Construction Project on the Land Plot.

The cost of land plots with capital construction facilities is higher than that of similar plots without such facilities. When conducting purchase and sale transactions, leases, pledges, and other transactions involving a land plot, the presence of a capital construction project is considered in forming the market price of the plot. Consequently, the market segments for developed and undeveloped plots may differ significantly.

5. Factor: Availability of a Well.

Providing a land plot with engineering infrastructure facilities is essential for forming supply in the land market. Additionally, the presence of a well on the plot contributes to its rational and efficient use. A water supply system not only meets the physiological needs of citizens for drinking resources (Golovina et al. 2023) but is also necessary for personal needs related to growing agricultural crops within the boundaries of the land plot in question.

6. Factor: Remoteness from Solid Waste Storage Areas.

When designing any GNPP, ANPP, or cottage village, designated areas for waste and garbage storage must be included. Since the territories of these associations are relatively small, such waste sites are typically located within walking distance. If a site is further away from solid waste storage areas, it becomes more attractive to potential buyers (SP 53.13330.2019... 2019) due to the absence of negative consequences like pollution of air, soil, water, green spaces, and other components of the natural environment. Environmental issues are particularly relevant today, with many Russian researchers assessing the current state of natural components, such as soils and green spaces, while offering various solutions of both theoretical and practical importance (Pashkevich et al. 2020; Skachkova & Guryeva 2023; Smirnov et al. 2021).

The factors considered shape supply and demand in the land market to varying degrees, leading to the conclusion that they influence both the market price and the cadastral value of the land plot. In this regard, an algorithm was proposed for determining the cadastral value of the land plots in question, taking into account the influence of local factors (see Fig. 4).

At the first stage, information was collected on offers and sales transactions for 400 land plots. Five GNPPs (Severyanye, Rassvet VOS-2, Domostroitel, Zelenaya Roshcha, and Zarya), located in different parts of the Belgorod district of the Belgorod region, were selected as objects of assessment. The choice of this list of GNPPs is based on the unique locations of the land plots; specifically, these plots are situated in areas with different types of soil and topography, which makes the study more comprehensive and visually informative (see Fig. 5).

The next stage involved the sequential vectorization of spatial information to calculate the values of relevant factors. The values of factors such as the distance to the railway station, water bodies, and solid waste storage areas were determined through a combination of partial field surveys of the analyzed GNPP territories and the interpretation of satellite images. Using data from soil and landscape maps of the Belgorod region, the soil types and relief features within each GNPP were identified. Soil quality, as a cost factor, was assessed in bonitet points (B). For this purpose, a soil map of the region was overlaid onto an electronic map containing cadastral blocks and land plots using the AutoCAD software (see Figure 6).

The soil types were identified using symbols, and the ratios of these soil types were determined along with their corresponding quality scores based on materials from NPO GeoGIS LLC. After analyzing data on the soils of the Belgorod region, four types of soils were established within the boundaries of the considered SNT: leached chernozems (B = 60), dark

Figure 4. Algorithm for calculating the cadastral value of land plots GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction. *Source:* Compiled by the authors

gray forest soils ($B = 58$), typical chernozems ($B = 62$), and gray forest soils ($B = 55$). The characteristics of the relief in the studied territories of the GNPP were determined similarly (Limited Liability Company... 2023).

Qualitative factors were specified as discrete values and accounted for using dummy variables, which range from 0 to 1, depending on the absence or presence of the required attribute, respectively. Adjustments to market data were made for auction prices and transaction dates, utilizing analytical information about the market value of the land plots in question. The amount of adjustment for the date of the transaction or offer was calculated quarterly, reflecting short-term fluctuations in offers during the exposure period. After collecting information on the qualitative and quantitative values of the factors, these values were ranked by dividing them into ranges and assigning serial numbers – ranks.

In this study, ranking was conducted for qualitative factors such as the type of surface of public roads, the relief within the GNPP, ANPP, the presence of a well, and the existence of a capital construction project on the land plot. Each factor was assigned discrete values of 0 and 1, and these indicators were normalized by dividing the assigned rank value by the maximum rank.

In the next stage, significance coefficients were calculated, and factors were assessed for multicollinearity using the Excel add-in “Data Analysis – Correlation.” We adhered to the criterion that two variables are considered collinear if the correlation coefficient between

Figure 5. Location of GNPP selected for assessment on the map of the Belgorod district. *Source:* Compiled by the authors

Figure 6. Overlay of GNPP on the soil map. *Source:* Compiled by the authors

them exceeds 0.75. It is important to note that the presence of multicollinearity among factors indicates the inclusion of factor characteristics that may overlap or the inclusion of linearly dependent factors in the model. To eliminate multicollinearity, one common method is to exclude one or more dependent variables. In this context, the decision to exclude a factor may not solely rely on the correlation coefficient value but also on existing information and a logical interpretation of the current market situation regarding the cost factors under consideration (Orlova & Filonova 2015).

To model the cadastral value of the land plots, the coefficients of the regression equation were calculated using the Excel add-in "Data Analysis – Regression."

Taking into account the collected market information and its analysis, preference was given to a linear regression model of the form:

$$y = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p), \quad (1)$$

which considers the characteristics of land plots (x_i) as independent variables, and the market value acts as a dependent variable (y), while each cost factor was introduced into the model by the sequential inclusion method (Gnat 2021). At each stage of entering factors, the quality of the resulting model was checked, taking into account the values of t-statistics ($t > 3$) and Significance F, the value of which should not exceed the specified reliability of the model ($\alpha = 0.05$).

When checking a regression model for compliance with the normal distribution law, it is necessary to take into account that the values of statistical significance do not exceed ($p < 0.05$) for each of the specified factors in the model.

Next, the resulting model was analyzed for homoscedasticity and autocorrelation in the residuals. Homoscedasticity assessment was performed using the Goldfeld–Quandt method. In accordance with this method, the following was done:

- 1) ordering observations according to one of the factors;
- 2) exclusion from the population (C) of central observations subject to the condition:

$$\frac{n-m}{2} > p, \quad (2)$$

where p is the number of parameters being assessed, C is the set of central observations, n is the number of factors;

- 3) dividing the remaining observations into two equal populations, constructing paired linear regression models;
- 4) determination of residual sums of squares for each of the groups (S_1, S_2) and determination of their ratio as for checking the direct and inverse dependence of the dispersion of residuals on the square of the factor:

$$F_{\text{obs}} = \frac{S_1}{S_2}, \quad (3)$$

where S_1, S_2 – observation groups.

It should be noted that the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity is satisfied provided that the ratio F_{obs} (3) will satisfy F_{crit} degrees of freedom for each residual sum of squares (Prokofiev & Savochkin 2013):

$$\frac{n-C-2p}{2} > p, \quad (4)$$

In this study, 400 observations were made, among which 100 central observations were excluded, resulting in two groups of 150 observations each. For each group, linear regression models were constructed, and the regression coefficients were determined (see Table 6). Next, the SICV was calculated, and the final stage involved determining the cadastral value of the plots in question using the example of GNPP “Severyane.”

Results

To implement the proposed methodology for determining the cadastral value of land plots in gardening non-profit partnerships (GNPP), agricultural non-profit partnerships (ANPP), and individual housing construction, a total of 400 plots were selected. This selection was made to ensure the sufficiency and representativeness of the sample.

Based on the analysis and processing of initial market data regarding local cost factors, the values of significance coefficients were obtained through correlation analysis. Additionally, these factors were checked for multicollinearity (see Table 2).

Table 2. Checking factors for multicollinearity

	Y	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	X ₇	X ₈	X ₉	X ₁₀
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Y	1										
X ₁	0.945	1									
X ₂	0.388	0.324	1								
X ₃	0.544	0.500	0.164	1							
X ₄	0.298	0.268	0.054	0.188	1						
X ₅	0.204	0.286	0.161	0.156	0.104	1					
X ₆	-0.228	-0.211	-0.110	-0.149	-0.046	-0.821	1				
X ₇	0.479	0.435	0.572	0.293	-0.200	0.127	-0.110	1			
X ₈	-0.161	-0.127	-0.081	-0.098	-0.101	-0.541	0.522	0.001	1		
X ₉	0.359	0.328	0.377	0.103	0.012	-0.221	0.170	0.421	0.172	1	
X ₁₀	-0.416	-0.374	-0.218	-0.272	-0.06	-0.837	0.807	-0.259	0.513	0.158	1

Source: authors’ calculations

Notes: X₁ – distance to the nearest settlement; X₂ – distance to the reservoir; X₃ – distance to the forest; X₄ – type of driveway surface; X₅ – distance to railway station; X₆ – soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction; X₇ – relief inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction, slope; X₈ – availability of a capital construction project on the land plot; X₉ – availability of a well; X₁₀ – remoteness from solid waste storage areas

The results of checking factors for multicollinearity showed a strong correlation between the factors: distance to railway station (X₅) and soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction (X₆); distance to railway station (X₅) and remoteness from solid waste storage areas (X₁₀); soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction (X₆) and remoteness from solid waste storage areas (X₁₀). The correlation coefficients for these

pairs exceeded 0.75. The relationship between factors (X_6) and (X_{10}) can be explained by the fact that a significant number of solid waste storage sites, combined with a high pH level in the waste, may lead to a deterioration in soil quality over time. Additionally, the relationship between factors (X_5) and (X_6) may indicate a possible misallocation of factor values, as these factors are not logically related.

Initially, the factor (X_1), which had the highest value of the pair correlation coefficient (-0.945), was included in the model. Subsequently, each factor was added sequentially, with the final list selected based on the primary condition of increasing the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2), which reflects the quality of the potential regression model. If the inclusion of a factor resulted in a decrease in the coefficient of determination (R^2), that factor was excluded from the model.

As a result of the analysis, only eight factors were identified as significant, having a greater impact on the market value of land plots. The inclusion of each of these eight factors in the model resulted in a multiple regression coefficient (R^2) ranging from 0.89 to 0.92, indicating the high significance and adequacy of the resulting model. The final regression model was constructed based on the following factors: X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , X_4 , X_6 , X_7 , X_9 , and X_{10} (see Table 3).

Table 3. Results of regression analysis

Regression statistics				
Plural R	0.96			
R-squared	0.92			
Normalized R-squared	0.92			
Standard error	4.10			
Observations	400			
	Coefficients	Standard error	t-statistics	P-meaning
Y- intersection	36.993	7.090	5.217	0.000
Distance to the nearest settlement (X_1)	3.285	0.084	39.237	0.000
Distance to the reservoir (X_2)	0.194	0.087	2.220	0.027
Distance to the forest (X_3)	0.689	0.148	4.648	0.000
Type of driveway surface (X_4)	2.033	0.472	4.306	0.000
Soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction (X_6)	0.291	0.134	3.182	0.030
Relief inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction, slope (X_7)	1.705	0.778	3.190	0.029
Availability of a well (X_9)	3.805	1.073	3.547	0.000
Remoteness from solid waste storage areas (X_{10})	-16.290	3.623	-4.496	0.000

Source: authors' calculations

Based on the results presented in Table 3, a linear regression model equation was compiled, which has the following form:

$$Y = 3,29 \cdot X_1 + 0,19 \cdot X_2 + 0,69 \cdot X_3 + 2,03 \cdot X_4 + 0,29 \cdot X_6 + 1,71 \cdot X_7 + 3,81 \cdot X_9 - 16,29 \cdot X_{10} + 36,9, \tag{3}$$

where Y – SICV, X₁ – distance to the nearest settlement; X₂ – distance to the reservoir; X₃ – distance to the forest; X₄ – type of driveway surface; X₆ – soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction; X₇ – relief inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction, slope; X₉ – availability of a well; X₁₀ – remoteness from solid waste storage areas.

At the next stage, the constructed regression model was tested for its statistical significance; “Significance F” did not exceed the reliability of the model (α = 0.05) (see Table 4).

Table 4. Results of statistical significance of the model

	df	SS	MS	F	Significance of F
1	2	3	4	5	6
Regression	8	73557.78	9194.723	547.644	0.000
Remainder	391	6564.73	16.796		
Total	399	80122.51			

Source: authors’ calculations

Testing the model for compliance of the values of cost factors and prices of similar objects with the normal distribution law revealed, as shown in Table 5, that the function adheres to the normal distribution law. This conclusion is supported by the statistical significance values for each of the specified factors, which do not exceed (p < 0.05).

Table 5. Results of statistical significance of factors

	P-value
1	2
Y- intersection	0.00000029
Distance to the nearest settlement (X ₁)	0.00000000
Distance to the reservoir (X ₂)	0.02698979
Distance to the forest (X ₃)	0.00000458
Type of driveway surface (X ₄)	0.00002101
Soil quality inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction (X ₆)	0.02968843
Relief inside GNPP, ANPP, individual housing construction, slope (X ₇)	0.02907391
Availability of a well (X ₉)	0.00043753
Remoteness from solid waste storage areas (X ₁₀)	0.00000912

Source: authors’ calculations

This was followed by an analysis of the regression model for homoscedasticity and auto-correlation in the residuals. Fisher’s criterion is determined according to the normative table of values F_{crit} at significance level (α=0.05) with the number of degrees of freedom k₁ = 8, k₂ = 141. Since F_{obs} < F_{crit} (see Table 6), the hypothesis of homoscedasticity of the residuals

was confirmed. This testing for homoscedasticity guarantees the reliability of the model's application and the validity of the obtained data. Additionally, it was essential to assess the autocorrelation among the residuals, for which the Durbin-Watson statistical test was employed, given the presence of a constant term in the equation (see Table 6).

Table 6. Results of residual sums of squares, Fobs, Durbin-Watson test

Indicators	Value
1	2
I-group (S_1)	1290.940
II-group (S_2)	3608.160
F_{obs}	2.794
F_{crit}	2.849
D_{obs}	1.731
D_1	1.500
D_2	2.500

Source: authors' calculations

According to the obtained results (see Table 6), there is no autocorrelation among the residuals. The determination of the SICV (Statistical Indicator of Cadastral Value) of land plots was carried out by substituting the values of each local cost factor into the established regression equation (see Table 7).

For a more visual representation of the results in determining the cadastral value of land plots, Figure 7 illustrates the zoning of the territory, using the example of GNPP "Severyane",

Figure 7. Zoning of the territory of GNPP "Severyane" according to SICV, taking into account the influence of local factors. Source: Compiled by the authors

Table 7. Results of determining the SICV of land plots

Nº	CN	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	X ₇	S _(ip)	Y _(mar)	SICV 2022	SICV new	SICV new - SICV 2022
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	31:15:0108011:1	3.902	5.630	5.072	1	0	0	0.3	810	64.391	55.42	69.031	13.61
2	31:15:0108011:10	2.228	1.526	1.352	0	0	0	0.3	357	57.503	55.42	58.138	2.72
3	31:15:0108011:11	2.174	1.472	1.316	0	0	0	0.3	472	57.257	55.42	57.926	2.51
4	31:15:0108011:12	3.362	11.111	5.588	1	0	0	0.3	550	62.669	55.42	68.093	12.67
5	31:15:0108011:13	1.256	4.060	0.86	0	0	0	0.3	600	53.444	55.42	55.098	-0.32
6	31:15:0108011:14	1.202	4.034	1.736	0	0	0	0.3	600	53.198	55.42	55.519	0.1
7	31:15:0108011:15	9.869	8.703	3.572	0	1	0	0.02	623	92.189	55.42	89.804	34.38
8	31:15:0108011:16	0.959	1.939	2.36	1	0	0	0.3	600	65.744	55.42	56.778	1.36
9	31:15:0108011:17	1.445	8.016	5.084	0	0	0	0.3	422	54.305	55.42	59.398	3.98
10	31:15:0108011:18	6.764	1.278	3.464	0	0	0	0.3	800	77.429	55.42	74.447	19.03
...													

Source: authors' calculations

based on the SICV obtained while considering the influence of local cost factors. The range of SICV values varies from 53 to 103 rubles/sq.m. It is noteworthy that land plots located within the boundaries of the soil variety “typical chernozems,” which has a bonitet score of 62, exhibit higher SICV values compared to plots situated within areas of soil varieties with lower bonitet scores. This observation is logical, as expected. Additionally, land plots that are within walking remoteness from solid waste storage sites have lower SICV values than those located farther away.

Based on the results presented in Table 8, the cadastral value of the land plots under consideration was calculated by multiplying the SICV by the area of each land plot (see Table 8).

Table 8. Results of determining the cadastral value of land plots

№	CN	S _{lp}	SICV ₂₀₂₂	CV ₂₀₂₂	SICV _{HOB}	CV _{HOB}
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	31:15:0111025:1	1000	65.36	65360	97.648	97648
2	31:15:0111025:10	623	65.36	40719.28	78.865	49132.90
3	31:15:0111025:100	800	65.36	52288	78.865	63092
4	31:15:0111025:101	800	65.36	52288	83.406	66724.80
5	31:15:0111025:102	800	65.36	52288	80.233	64186.40
6	31:15:0111025:103	800	65.36	52288	82.118	65694.40
7	31:15:0111025:29	350	65.36	22876	57.618	20166.30
8	31:15:0111025:30	593	65.36	38758.48	56.237	33348.54
9	31:15:0111025:73	519	65.36	33921.84	59.792	31032.05
10	31:15:0111025:65	810	65.36	52941.60	64.725	52427.25
...						

Source: authors' calculations

The algorithm of the proposed methodology enabled the determination of cadastral values for the land plots under consideration, falling within the range of their market values and accurately reflecting the current market situation.

Conclusions

Based on the above analysis, we can conclude the following:

1. Importance of Land Resources: land resources are crucial raw materials for the country's future development and require effective public administration (Litvinenko et al. 2023). In a market economy, these resources serve as economic assets and are strategic for the nation's food security (Lukhno 2023), while also supporting local budgets. As objects of economic relations, land resources must be assessed – both market and cadastral valuations – accurately, reliably, and objectively. However, the analysis of existing research reveals challenges in cadastral land valuation methodologies, prompting the scientific community to seek solutions.
2. Local Cost Factors: the study identifies local cost factors that significantly influence market pricing for gardening and vegetable gardening plots (GNPP), agricultural

non-profit partnerships (ANPP), and individual housing construction. These factors should be integral to determining cadastral values for land taxation purposes.

3. **Proposed Methodology:** the proposed algorithm for the cadastral valuation of land plots in the “Gardening and Vegetable Gardening, Low-Rise Residential Development” segment, specifically for the Belgorod region, models the influence of local factors, including distance to the nearest settlement, water bodies, forests, access road surfaces, soil quality, terrain relief, well presence, and proximity to solid waste storage sites, within the context of an active land market.
4. **Linear Model Justification:** the application of a linear model for calculating the site-improvement cadastral value (SICV) in this segment has been justified, demonstrating reliability and validity in the resulting data.
5. **Model Testing:** the model was tested using land plots from GNPP in the Belgorod Region. The results indicated that the differences between cadastral and market values for the “Green Roshcha” and “Domostroitel” plots were 14.3% and 15.7%, respectively, while for “Zarya” and “Rassvet,” the differences were 11.2% and 7.7%, showing a decrease in cadastral value relative to market value and reflecting values closer to market assessments. Notably, previous assessments from the State Defense Committee in 2022 showed a disparity of 45.5%, underscoring the rationality and effectiveness of the proposed methodology.
6. **Comparative Results:** comparing the cadastral values from the State Defense Committee of 2022 with those from this study revealed an increase in the coefficient of determination for the linear regression model from 0.77 to 0.92, indicating a high degree of reliability in the results obtained. Additionally, the average cadastral value across all land plots decreased by 12.2%, further validating the need to consider local cost factors.

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